

FURTHER IMPROVEMENT OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF MOBILITY OF THE BASE MOVEMENT APPARATUS IN THE FORMATION OF MOVEMENT SKILLS OF YOUNG WRESTLERS

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Abstract: This article provides ideas among wrestling coaches that they still do not have a unanimous opinion on the issues of organizing and conducting sports training in sports schools, so that the system of training sports coaches should also be further improved. The results of the study made it possible to identify a number of important issues related to the problem of developing aparati mobility of the support movement of young wrestlers, and at the same time it was found that physical qualities are of great importance in ensuring the comprehensive physical fitness of young wrestlers.

Keywords: physical fitness, sports training, physical qualities, aparati mobility of the base movement, young wrestlers.

ДАЛЬНЕЙШЕЕ СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ РАЗВИТИЯ ПОДВИЖНОСТИ ОПОРНОГО АППАРАТА ПРИ ФОРМИРОВАНИИ ДВИГАТЕЛЬНЫХ НАВЫКОВ ЮНЫХ БОРЦОВ

Аннотация: В данной статье приводятся идеи среди тренеров по борьбе о том, что у них до сих пор нет единого мнения по вопросам организации и проведения спортивной подготовки в спортивных школах, в связи с чем система подготовки спортивных тренеров также должна быть в дальнейшем усовершенствована. Результаты исследования позволили выделить ряд важных вопросов, связанных с проблемой развития подвижности опорного аппарата юных борцов, и в то же время установлено, что физические качества имеют большое значение в обеспечении комплексной физической подготовленности юных борцов.

Ключевые слова: физическая подготовленность, спортивная подготовка, физические качества, подвижность опорного аппарата, юные борцы.

RELEVANCE AND NECESSITY OF THE SUBJECT

At the world level, interest in the sport of wrestling increases, with a special emphasis on development among young people and adults. The cultivation of talented athletes in Olympic and national sports regularly leads to a sharpening of competition, an increase in the intensity of the training process at the level of demand. This is encouraging the formation and research of new styles in terms of improving the way wrestlers are trained. In particular, as a result of continental premierships, competitions held in the world championship circuit, the sport of wrestling has been gaining a foothold in the world community. In the above competitions, in order to ensure the participation of wrestlers, large-scale work is being carried out to adapt the system of training young wrestlers to the requirements of the Times. One of the most important tasks facing all types of wrestling today, the issue of developing the mobility of the base movement apparatus through correct and effective methods is gaining relevance in the formation of movement skills of young wrestlers. To a certain extent, this work study will serve the implementation of the tasks reflected in PQ-4881 of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan on November 4, 2020 “on measures to

develop the National Sport Of Wrestling and further increase its international prestige”, PQ-3306 of October 2, 2017 “on measures to further develop the National Sport Of Wrestling” and regulatory legal acts related to.

THE DEGREE OF STUDY OF THE PROBLEM

In the development of mobility of the base movement apparatus of young wrestlers, the demand for the development of new scientific and theoretical approaches to the many-year stages of their training is an urgent problem. In solving the above problems, a number of scientists conducted scientific research. Including A.Attoyev, K.Yusupov, J.Toshpolatov, U.Ibrahimov, Z.Jumayev, A.R.Taimuratov, Z.S.Artikov, O.V.Goncharov, F.A.Kerimov and others conducted scientific research and developed a new proposal and recommendations that substantiated the system of pre-competition preparation in their textbooks, manuals, articles and theses. The results of the scientific research carried out by these scientists are worthy of special attention and are currently being used in this area. Despite the systematic research carried out, the training requires the development of additional scientific, scientific and methodological developments related to the development of mobility of the base movement apparatus in the formation of movement skills of young wrestlers, selected as the subject of this dissertation in methodological and scientific sources.

The purpose of the study is to develop proposals and recommendations for further improvement of the development of mobility of the base movement apparatus in the formation of movement skills of young wrestlers.

Objectives of the study:

In the development of mobility of the support movement apparatus of young wrestlers, the development of a mechanism of the application of meiorized loadings; Development of a methodology for the use of dynamic, static and statodynamic exercises, in the development of mobility of the musculoskeletal apparatus of young wrestlers;

The object of the study is the Sports School No. 1 of the Samarkand region, Samarkand district, in the initial preparatory groups, a training process was taken aimed at the development of mobility of the base movement apparatus in the formation of movement skills of young wrestlers.

Scientific innovation of research

In the development of the mobility of the base movement apparatus in the formation of movement skills of young wrestlers, a mechanism for the use of special exercises has been developed that help to develop general flexibility based on the application of meiorized loadings; In the development of the mobility of the base movement apparatus in the formation of movement skills of young wrestlers, due to the improvement of the methodology for the use of dynamic, static and statodynamic exercises, a feature of the interaction between different types of approximating exercises and quantitative measurement measures have been developed;

Practical results of the study

Training efficiency has been increased due to the development of the mechanics of the use of special exercises that help young wrestlers to develop general flexibility in the development of the mobility of the support movement apparatus, the application of meticolated loadings;

In the development of mobility of the support movement apparatus of young wrestlers, due to the improvement of the methodology for using dynamic, static and statodynamic exercises, a tool aimed at improving the specificity of the interaction between the various approximating exercises and quantitative measurement criteria, methods were used in the training of wrestlers at the initial stage of training;

The main stages of conducting pedagogical experience:

Stage I (2019-2020)-a detailed analysis of previously published work on this topic; identification of unresolved problems, selection of this research topic; setting the purpose and objectives of the study; study of real practice on solving this problem; study of measures contained in the theory and methodology of physical education and helping to solve this problem; formulate a research hypothesis.

Phase II (2020-2021) consists of a number of tasks: selection of experimental objects (wrestlers) in the required amount; determination of the necessary duration of the experiment, selection of specific methodologies for studying the initial state of the object of the experiment; testing the convenience and effectiveness of methodologies in a small number of Examiners; identification of signs and factors

Phase III (2021-2022) is the main, it is intended to conduct an experiment to verify the effectiveness of the developed methodology. This stage includes the following measures: to study the initial state of the framework of the system in which the experiment is carried out (the level of physical and technical-tactical training of the wrestlers is determined); to study the initial state of the conditions under which the experiment is carried out; to form the norms of effectiveness of the proposed measures, to give; record data representing changes in objects under the influence of the system of experimental activities, show difficulties and possible typical shortcomings during the conduct of the experiment; assess the current consumption of time, tools and efforts.

Stage IV (2022-2023) - finisher, intended to end the experiment: highlight the results of the implementation of the experimental event system; describe the conditions in which the experiment gave the desired results; describe the characteristics of the subjects of experimental influence (coaches, athletes); determine information about the consumption of time, efforts and tools; indicate the limits of the application of the

There are several ways to develop flexibility, including. The manual necessary for the development of flexibility of primary school-age children engaged in methodological development, struggle provides theoretical materials and practical recommendations, as well as samples of exercises. The development of flexibility, that is, mobility, is aimed at increasing the amplitude of movement on the wrist, shoulder girdle, spine in different parts of the body. Flexibility is one of the most important for a person, being one of the physical qualities. The development of various programs for the development of flexibility is mainly associated with the development of sports such as sports and rhythmic gymnastics, acrobatics, figure skating, wrestling. In the theory and methodology of sports training, the concept of flexibility refers to the ability to perform movements in joints with maximum amplitude. Under the influence of exercises on the development of flexibility in the organism of young wrestlers, the opportunity is created to effectively master technical actions. (Table 1).

Table 1. The effect of exercises on the development of flexibility on the organism of young wrestlers

To the muscles	elastic properties improve
	power quality improves
	recovery processes improve after loading
	reduced risk of injury
	the ability to relax improves

To the external and internal organs of my organism	Improved mobility
	metabolic processes improve
	prevents arthrosis
Spinal cord	muscle balance decreases,
	prevents osteochondrosis
To the nervous system	the ability to relax improves

Elasticity depends on what degree of manifestation of elasticity depends on a number of different factors. Flexibility depends on mobility in a particular joint, which is determined by its anatomical structure and, above all, the shape of the articular surfaces. The mobility of the musculoskeletal apparatus is influenced by a number of factors, including the content of hormones such as elastin and collagen in the connective tissue, their mechanical properties. Elastin determines the elasticity of tissues, the strength of collagen, and their ratio in the body characterizes the degree of development of elasticity to a certain extent. The Daily periodical also plays its own roll.

The most sensitive period for the development of elasticity is 7-9 years old. Flexibility continues to develop successfully, but at a lower pace until the age of 12-13, the level of mobility in the joints worsens. Passive flexibility is manifested due to the influence of forces outside the body and depends on the elasticity and length of the muscles around the joint. Active flexibility depends on the same factors, as well as the strength of the muscles that surround the joint and are able to move with one or another amplitude. The relationship between the two types of elasticity and the qualities of strength with each other is unclear. Improving passive flexibility leads to improved active flexibility.

Flexibility determines the level of sportsmanship in the fight. Insufficient development of flexibility slows down the process of mastering movement skills, cannot reveal the activity of speed, strength, coordination abilities, and also reduces work unimagability, limiting movement and causing muscle injury.

Lack of flexibility is the cause of a decrease in the effectiveness of training aimed at training other qualities. Insufficient mobility in the joints does not allow us to use the elastic properties of the muscles to increase the efficiency of work performed by force, limiting the possibilities of training techniques aimed at increasing the capabilities of work movements and improving coordination. Flexibility in wrestling depends on training, as well as the effectiveness of the competitions on their development. With the development of the body, the elasticity also changes unevenly. Thus, the mobility of the spine during tulip growth increases significantly in boys between the ages of 7 and 14, while in girls between the ages of 7 and 12, the increase in flexibility decreases in adulthood. High levels of Flexion are reported in boys aged 15, girls aged 14, with active movements having slightly less flexion than passives.

Mobility in the movements of the shoulder girdle at the joints increases until the age of 12-13, with the highest results being 9-10 years old. The growth of mobility is from 7 to 10 years old, in subsequent years the growth of flexibility slows down and by the age of 13-14 approaches the indicators of adults. In people of different ages, there is a negative relationship between the flexibility and strength of the muscles with the strengthening of the muscles as a result of training, as a rule, mobility in the joints decreases. The degree of development of elasticity is influenced by hereditary and environmental factors. During human life, the size of the articular surfaces, the

elasticity of the apparatus of the movement of the support, changes significantly. Naturally, therefore, the amount of mobility in joints of different ages is not the same. In wrestlers, exercises are used that can be performed with a maximum amplitude as a means of developing flexibility. The main limitations of the range of Motion are the antagonist muscles. Stretching the connective tissue of these muscles, making the muscles flexible and elastic is the task of stretching exercises. Active, passive and static stand out among stretching exercises. Full amplitude active movements (vibrations of the arms and legs, bends and rotational movements of the body) can be performed without objects and with objects (gymnastic sticks, rings, balls, etc. Passive flexibility exercises include the following, actions performed with the help of a partner; movements performed with weights, movements performed using a rubber resistance band or shock absorber, passive movements using their own strength (pulling the body to the legs, bending the hand with the other hand, etc.), movements performed on projectiles.

Static exercises performed with body weight or strength take 6-9 C for a certain period of time. limited amplitude requires maintenance of a stationary state. Exercises aimed at developing flexibility are based on the performance of various movements, bending and twisting, rotational movements. Such exercises can be performed independently, with different weights or the simplest training devices (on the gymnastic wall, with gymnastic sticks, etc.). These exercises may be aimed at developing mobility in all joints to improve overall flexibility. When improving special flexibility, special preparatory exercises are used that have a targeted effect on the joints, in which Mobility most determines the success of professional and sports activities. By purposefully performing special exercises, much greater flexibility can be achieved than is required in the process of professional actions. This creates a certain “reserve of elasticity”. The exercises performed can be active, passive and mixed, and can also be performed in dynamic, static or mixed statodynamic mode. the development of active flexibility is facilitated by self-performed exercises, which include exercises with body weight and external weight.

In a word, struggle is an activity that is multifaceted, emotional, natural and at the same time open to many. In order to improve the skills of the leading wrestlers of the national teams (effective transfer of high-speed techniques in competitions), the work must be re-mastered, first of all, with young people. The rules of competitions, technical training are being improved and the requirements for the athlete are changing. Therefore, it is necessary to try to determine the dynamics of the development of the struggle, taking into account national traditions and the world trend. We used the following control test criteria to determine the degree of development of the quality of flexibility in wrestlers in the initial training phase (table 2)

Table 2. Control exercises (tests) used to determine the level of development of flexibility abilities of wrestlers

T/r	Control exercises	Exercise content	Assessment indicators
1	Exercise in bridge position in wrestling (most). 30 p.	Standing with heads and hands resting on the ground, and bending and writing feet	Time
2	Rotation about the axis of the head 30 s.	Standing with heads and hands resting on the ground, and with legs rotating around the axis of the head	Time

3	Holding static position in bridge position (seconds)	Standing with heads and hands resting on the ground, legs in an inscribed position	Capture Time (s).
4	In the case of a bridge, jumping forward and backward around the head axis is 30 s.	In the bridge position, jumping back and forth around the head axis is in the position where the arms and head are not disconnected from the ground	Time
5	90 c0 static position holding while hanging on the turnstile	Holding the leg at an angle of 900	Capture Time (s).
6	Measure flexibility while leaning forward in the gymnast's seat	Measure flexibility with the gymnast leaning forward in her seat, in which the knees are not bent, measuring the tip of the arms	sm

Training in the position of the bridge in wrestling (most) 30 s. Rotation about the axis of the head 30 s. Holding a static position in the bridge position (seconds). In the case of a bridge, jumping forward and backward around the head axis is 30 s. Holding a 90 c0 static position while hanging on the turnstile. Measure flexibility (CM) with the gymnast leaning forward in her seat. We used test criteria.

Control exercises (tests) used to determine the level of development of flexibility abilities of 9-10-year-old wrestlers were distinguished, and the mobility of the support movement apparatus of 24 young wrestlers was analyzed at the beginning of the study. In this case, the indicators for 6 control exercises were studied by us. These are exercises in the position of the bridge in the fight (most). 30 p., rotation about the head Axis 30 s., holding the static position in the bridge position (seconds), jumping around the head Axis back and forth in the bridge position is 30 s., holding a 90 c0 static position while hanging on the turnstile., measuring flexibility with forward tilt in the gymnastics seat (sm) with the adoption of these test criteria, the flexibility of the support movement apparatus was determined (Table 3).

Table 3. Control exercises (tests) used to determine the level of development of flexibility abilities of wrestlers 9-10 years old (n=24).

T/r	Control exercises	At the beginning of the study				t	P
		Experimental group		Control group			
		$(\bar{X} \pm \sigma)$	V	$(\bar{X} \pm \sigma)$	V		
1	Exercise in bridge position in wrestling (most). 30 p.	15,9±1,2	7,8	16,1±1,6	9,8	0,6	P>0,05
2	Rotation about the axis of the head 30 s.	10,5±1,1	10,3	10,7±0,9	8,9	0,9	P>0,05
3	Holding static position in bridge position (seconds)	12,8±1,4	10,9	12,5±1,4	11,6	0,8	P>0,05
4	In the case of a bridge, jumping forward and backward around	15,8±0,9	5,9	16,2±0,8	5,3	1,6	P>0,05

	the head axis is 30 s.						
5	Holding a 90 c0 static position while hanging on the turnstile.	11,2±1,3	11,4	11,6±0,9	8,4	1,3	P>0,05
6	Measure flexibility (CM) with the gymnast leaning forward in her seat.	10,2±1,4	11,8	10,9±1,3	12,1	1,8	P>0,05

Control exercises (tests) used to determine the level of development of elasticity qualities of wrestlers 11-12 years old were distinguished, and the mobility of the support movement apparatus of 24 young wrestlers was analyzed at the beginning of the study. In this case, the indicators for 6 control exercises were studied by us (Table 4).

Table 4. Control exercises (tests) used to determine the level of development of flexibility abilities of wrestlers 11-12 years old.

T/r	Control exercises	At the beginning of the study				t	P
		Experimental group		Control group			
		($\bar{X} \pm \sigma$)	V	($\bar{X} \pm \sigma$)	V		
1	Exercise in bridge position in wrestling (most). 30 p.	20,2±1,1	5,2	20,7±1,6	7,7	1,3	P>0,05
2	Rotation about the axis of the head 30 s.	12,8±1,4	10,9	12,5±1,4	11,5	0,8	P>0,05
3	Holding static position in bridge position (seconds)	13,1±1,2	9,1	13,5±1,2	9,2	0,9	P>0,05
4	In the case of a bridge, jumping forward and backward around the head axis is 30 s.	20,3±1,4	6,7	20,9±1,5	7,2	1,4	P>0,05
5	Holding a 90 c0 static position while hanging on the turnstile.	16,6±1,1	6,9	17,1±1,5	8,8	1,1	P>0,05
6	Measure flexibility (CM) with the gymnast leaning forward in her seat.	12,4±1,4	11,6	12,8±1,5	11,9	0,9	P>0,05

Exercise in bridge position in wrestling (most). 30 p. In the control range, the study ohir, it was found that the experimental group had 17.5±1.1 seconds and the control group had 16.5±1.4 seconds. T=2.7; p<0.05; statistical reliable differences were observed between indicators. Rotation about the axis of the head 30 s. In the control range, the study ohir, it was found that the experimental group had 12.1±1.6 seconds and the control group had 11.2±0.9 seconds. T=2.4; p<0.05; statistical reliable differences were observed between indicators. In the bridge State, static attitude capture (seconds), in the control range, in the study range, was found to be 14.4±2.1 seconds in the experimental group and 13.1±1.6 seconds in the control group. T=2.3; p<0.05; statistical reliable differences were observed between indicators. In the case of a bridge, jumping forward and backward around the head axis is 30 s. In the control range, the study ohir, it was found that the experimental group had 17.5±1.4 seconds and the control group had 16.6±0.9 seconds. T=2.4; p<0.05; statistical reliable differences were observed between indicators. Holding

a 90 c0 static position while hanging on the turnstile. In the control range, the study ohir, it was found that the experimental group had 13.3±1.8 seconds and the control group had 12.1±1.7 seconds. T=2.2; p<0.05; statistical reliable differences were observed between indicators. Measure flexibility (CM) with the gymnast leaning forward in her seat. In the control range, the study ohir, it was found that the experimental group had 13.5±1.5 seconds and the control group had 11.7±1.6 seconds. T=3.8; p<0.05; statistical reliable differences were observed between indicators (Table 5).

Table 5. Control exercises (tests) used to determine the level of development of flexibility abilities of 9-10-year-old wrestlers.

T/r	Control exercises	In the field of research				t	P
		Experimental group		Control group			
		($\bar{X} \pm \sigma$)	V	($\bar{X} \pm \sigma$)	V		
1	Exercise in bridge position in wrestling (most). 30 p.	17,5±1,1	6,1	16,5±1,4	8,7	2,7	P<0,05
2	Rotation about the axis of the head 30 s.	12,1±1,6	13,1	11,2±0,9	8,5	2,4	P<0,05
3	Holding static position in bridge position (seconds)	14,4±2,1	14,1	13,1±1,6	12,1	2,3	P<0,05
4	In the case of a bridge, jumping forward and backward around the head axis is 30 s.	17,5±1,4	7,9	16,6±0,9	5,9	2,4	P<0,05
5	Holding a 90 c0 static position while hanging on the turnstile.	13,3±1,8	13,6	12,1±1,7	14,3	2,2	P<0,05
6	Measure flexibility (CM) with the gymnast leaning forward in her seat.	13,5±1,5	11,2	11,7±1,6	14,1	3,8	P<0,001

Training 11-12-year-old wrestlers in a bridge position in wrestling (most), in determining their flexibility abilities. 30 p. In the control range, the study ohir, it was found that the experimental group had 22.3±1.3 seconds and the control group had 21.2±1.8 seconds. T=2.3; p<0.05; statistical reliable differences were observed between indicators. Rotation about the axis of the head 30 s. In the control range, the study ohir, it was found that the experimental group had 14.2±0.7 seconds and the control group had 13.2±1.3 seconds. Between indicators t=3.1; P<0.01; statistical reliable differences were observed. In the bridge State, static attitude capture (seconds), in the control range, in the study range, was found to be 17.7±1.9 seconds in the experimental group and 16.7±1.4 seconds in the control group. T=2.2; p<0.05; statistical reliable differences were observed between indicators. In the case of a bridge, jumping forward and backward around the head axis is 30 s. In the control range, the study ohir, it was found that the experimental group had 23.2±2.1 seconds and the control group had 21.8±2.1 seconds. T=2.5; p<0.05; statistical reliable differences were observed between the indicators. Holding a 90 c0 static position while hanging on the turnstile. In the control range, the study ohir, it was found that the experimental group had 19.1±1.4 seconds and the control group had 17.9±2.2 seconds. T=2.4; p<0.05; statistical

reliable differences were observed between indicators. Measure flexibility (CM) with the gymnast leaning forward in her seat. In the control range, the study ohir, it was found that the experimental group had 14.9 ± 1.8 seconds and the control group had 13.3 ± 1.6 seconds. $T=3.1$; $p<0.05$; statistical reliable differences were observed between indicators. (Table 6).

Table 6. Control exercises (tests) used to determine the level of development of flexibility abilities of wrestlers 11-12 years old.

T/r	Control exercises	In the field of research				t	P
		Experimental group		Control group			
		$(\bar{X} \pm \sigma)$	V	$(\bar{X} \pm \sigma)$	V		
1	Exercise in bridge position in wrestling (most). 30 p.	$22,3 \pm 1,3$	5,8	$21,2 \pm 1,8$	8,5	2,3	$P<0,05$
2	Rotation about the axis of the head 30 s.	$14,2 \pm 0,7$	5,3	$13,2 \pm 1,3$	10,2	3,1	$P<0,01$
3	Holding static position in bridge position (seconds)	$17,7 \pm 1,9$	10,7	$16,7 \pm 1,4$	8,1	2,2	$P<0,05$
4	In the case of a bridge, jumping forward and backward around the head axis is 30 s.	$23,2 \pm 2,1$	9,1	$21,8 \pm 2,1$	9,7	2,5	$P<0,05$
5	Holding a 90 c0 static position while hanging on the turnstile.	$19,1 \pm 1,4$	7,6	$17,9 \pm 2,2$	12,2	2,4	$P<0,05$
6	Measure flexibility (CM) with the gymnast leaning forward in her seat.	$14,9 \pm 1,8$	12,2	$13,3 \pm 1,6$	12,5	3,1	$P<0,05$

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the scientific and methodological literature and the research carried out and the results obtained from them, the following conclusions were formed: 1. The results of theoretical analysis and generalization of scientific and methodological literature on the problems of training wrestlers, as well as the work experience of leading coaches, allow you to draw some conclusions, modern theory and practice, from a combinatorial understanding of the style of wrestling, wrestling if one combination consists of 2-3 different technical actions, the wrestler approached the style of Situational combat requires confidence, the ability to use the strength of the opponent, self-confidence and, based on flexibility and acrobatic training, the development of physical ability (readiness) to perform any technical action necessary at the moment. 2. Since the theoretical biomechanics of struggle is at the level of initial formation, it is possible to use modeling and analysis in a general sense, working with basic concepts in the practical analysis of technical-tactical actions. It is necessary to develop mobility, physical qualities, before learning the technique, otherwise the skill can later turn into a brake, it is much more difficult to re-learn after the appearance of physical qualities, the struggle of general and special physical qualities in sports (strength, speed and endurance) is closely related to the peculiarities of sports, flexibility allows you to The effective use of gymnastic exercises in the preparatory and final part of training in the

step-by-step training of flexibility allows wrestlers to develop the mobility of the musculoskeletal apparatus. 3. The fact that highly developed inter-joint flexibility has a positive effect on technical and tactical methods has been proven in types of struggle is noted in the sources. Such results were also confirmed by the results of a study in wrestlers with poor elasticity and well-developed abilities. Another extremely important, previously unexplored issue from current research has been clarified that the maximum and explosive strength indicators determined using computerized measuring equipment in wrestlers with poor flexibility have been proven in the study to be lower than those of wrestlers who have found good polished flexibility.

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